

IMPROVEMENT OF THE CATERING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article examines the issues of development and improvement of the hotel industry in Uzbekistan and analyzes the main factors contributing to the development of this sector. The study emphasizes the modernization of hotel infrastructure, improving the quality of service, the introduction of digital technologies, the development of international cooperation and the support of sustainable tourism. Statistics for 2023-2024 show that the number of hotels in Uzbekistan is growing rapidly. The study highlights that the introduction of innovative technologies, the provision of tax incentives and the adoption of eco-tourism strategies contribute to the sustainable development of the hotel industry. In addition, the integration of hotels into a single management system will help to strengthen competition and improve the quality of service. These measures are aimed at making Uzbekistan one of the leading tourist destinations in the region and ensuring long-term economic benefits.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, hotel industry, tourism development, quality of service, digitalization, sustainable tourism.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is actively working for the accelerated development of tourism sector. During this process, the improvement of the hotel system is one of the priority areas that can turn the country into one of the leading tourist centers in the region by developing a modern infrastructure, improving the quality of service and creating favorable conditions that meet international requirements. Maasalan: Modernization of hotel infrastructure by 2024 the number of hotels in Uzbekistan will reach 1,442. This figure shows that 833 new hotels have been commissioned in the last four years. The number of rooms was 33,4 thousand units, and the number of beds was 71,2 thousand. It is important to renovate or reconstruct hotel buildings using modern architectural styles and environmentally friendly materials. The design of the rooms

should include modern comfort, be as comfortable and modern as possible for guests. Improving the quality of services In 2023, the volume of accommodation and catering services amounted to 18,300.2 billion soums, which shows an increase of 311.3% compared to 2020. Of these, the volume of subsistence services reached 2,745.03 billion soums, which is 15% of the total. It is necessary to improve the skills of hotel staff, raise the standards of customer service to the international level. Employees need to constantly develop their knowledge and skills through training and seminars. Also, the introduction of a multilingual system of services will create great convenience for foreign tourists. Introduction of digital technology Hotel operations can improve customer experience by introducing modern online reservation systems, artificial intelligence and automated service technologies. Electronic payment systems, smart room management systems and interactive services ensure the convenience of guests. These technologies are also positively impacting the increase in the number of users of hotel services. Strengthening international cooperation In 2024, hotels under Azimut, Bentley, Bill Wyndham & Co were opened in Tashkent. Also, the 4-star hotel "Hilton Garden Inn Termez Airitom" in Termez and "Dedeman Hotel" in Navoi have started operations. Hotels under the Hilton Samarkand Regency, Hilton Garden Inn Samarkand Healthy and Intercontinental brands were opened in Samarkand Tourism Center. Through cooperation with leading international hotel chains, it is possible to introduce a new business model and management methods for hotels in Uzbekistan, and it is necessary to combine existing hotels under one system, which will create competitive conditions for all hotels, prices, conditions and hotels, and they will be able to follow the news in hotels. Tax Incentives and Supports for Hotel Business From October 1, 2024 to November 1, 2026, subsidies will be provided for newly established modular hotels with a certificate of compliance and consisting of at least 10 modules. The subsidy is set at 1 million soums for each place created in a modular hotel. The construction of new hotels should be encouraged by the government by providing tax incentives and loans for the hotel business. Also, further rapid development of the industry can be achieved by expanding investment support programs for local entrepreneurs. Ecotourism and sustainable development Building eco-friendly hotels and the use of green energy will ensure the long-term sustainability of the hotel business. Taking into account the natural beauty of Uzbekistan, the development of hotels oriented towards ecotourism is of great importance. In addition, sustainable development can be achieved through waste recycling and the implementation of water and energy saving technologies. Improvement of hotel system in Uzbekistan is the important step for further development of tourism sector. Reforms carried out on the

basis of the above directions will contribute to the development of not only domestic, but also international tourism. This, in turn, will have a positive effect on the economy of the country and help turn Uzbekistan into a more attractive destination on the global tourist map. Also, sustainable growth of the tourism industry can be achieved by ensuring innovative development and competitiveness of the hotel business.

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